

Using Reinforcement Learning for Security Testing: A Systematic Mapping Study

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Abstract—Security of software systems has become increasingly important due to the advancement in technology that occurs on a daily basis and due to the interconnectivity that the Internet network system provides. The manual testing process is time-consuming process and inefficient, especially for very large and complex systems. Reinforcement learning has shown promising results in different test generation approaches due to its ability to optimize the test generation process towards relevant parts of the system. A considerable body of work has been developed in recent years to exploit reinforcement learning for security test generation. This study provides a list of approaches and tools for security test generation using Reinforcement Learning (RL). By searching popular research publication databases, a list of 47 relevant studies has been identified and classified according to the type of approach, RL algorithm, application domain and publication metadata.

Index Terms—security testing, test generation, AI-assisted software testing, reinforcement learning, systematic mapping study

address specific aspects of system vulnerability. *Penetration testing* is a security testing approach where a tester checks the System Under Test (SUT) against known attacks and observes any unexpected behaviour [2]. Penetration testers leverage their comprehensive understanding of system architecture and code to uncover potential intrusion points. *Vulnerability scanning* utilizes specialized tools and scripts to detect vulnerabilities based on predefined knowledge bases and payload databases [1]. This approach is particularly effective for applications that rely on diverse network communications. Common tools employed in vulnerability testing include Nessus and OpenVAS. *Fuzzing* or *fuzz testing* [3] is a testing methodology where the SUT is fed with invalid and unexpected input data in order to find vulnerabilities. The effectiveness of fuzzing relies heavily on the design of input generation policies to achieve higher efficiency and broader coverage of the software under examination.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the security of software systems has become increasingly critical due to rapid technological advancements and the widespread adoption of the Internet. In this interconnected era, software systems with vulnerabilities pose substantial threats to public organizations and private enterprises alike. The potential consequences of these threats range from service quality degradation, such as disruptions in telecommunication services, to severe risks to human life, exemplified by malicious attacks on critical infrastructure controllers like those in nuclear power plants.

To address these challenges and ensure the resilience and security of software systems, security testing has emerged as a crucial component of the software development lifecycle. Security testing encompasses a comprehensive evaluation of software systems, aimed at identifying and assessing vulnerabilities, weaknesses, and potential risks across software, hardware, and network components [1]. This process is essential for evaluating system security against various security aspects and improving the overall robustness of the system.

By identifying security risks at different stages of the software lifecycle, developers and other stakeholders can address weak points in the system, despite the growing complexity of modern software ecosystems. There are several distinct approaches to security testing, each designed to

RL brings several notable benefits to security testing. By learning from trial and error, RL can adapt to new scenarios and identify optimal strategies for uncovering vulnerabilities. RL agents, and RL systems learn continuously from new data and scenarios, adapting to emerging threats and vulnerabilities in real-time, which allows to discover non-intuitive vulnerabilities and attack vectors, leading to more robust security testing. In addition, traditional cybersecurity testing techniques, such as penetration testing or vulnerability scanning, are labour-intensive and rely heavily on expert knowledge. RL can automate these processes by training intelligent agents to simulate attacks, identify vulnerabilities, and evaluate defences, thus increasing the scalability of the security testing process. Furthermore, cybersecurity scenarios often involve large state and action spaces, such as thousands of potential attack paths in a network or permutations of input fuzzing for testing software. RL algorithms can efficiently explore these spaces and focus on actions with the highest likelihood of success.

This paper presents a systematic mapping study (SMS) of the existing literature on security testing approaches using RL, which have been published in the last 10 years. The goal of this study is to provide a comprehensive overview of the research landscape, identify key trends, and highlight potential research directions. The SMS will be based on the guidelines that are described by Petersen et al. [4].

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II outlines the research methodology used for the systematic mapping study, including the steps taken to identify relevant literature, extract key information, and analyse the results. Section III presents the results of the literature search and analysis. The section will also delve into the specific applications of RL in security testing, such as penetration and fuzzing testing. Section IV highlights the key themes and contributions, and promising directions for future research. Section V discusses the limitations and threats to the validity of our study. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper with a brief overview of the main contributions and implications of the systematic mapping study, emphasizing the potential benefits of RL for improving security testing practices.

A. Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement Learning (RL) [5] is a reward-driven machine learning technique where an agent learns optimal actions through trial and error. The RL framework consists of an agent, environment, actions, states, and rewards, with the goal of maximizing cumulative rewards over time. Policies, either deterministic or stochastic, govern action selection, while value functions estimate expected returns. Many RL algorithms are formulated as Markov Decision Processes (MDPs), where state transitions and rewards depend only on the current state and action.

RL algorithms used in security testing fall into four categories:

Value-Based Methods estimate action values to derive policies. Q-Learning [6] approximates optimal values iteratively, while Deep Q-Networks (DQN) [7] stabilize learning with experience replay and fixed Q-targets. Double DQN (DDQN) [8] mitigates overestimation bias, and Dueling DQN [9] enhances policy evaluation. Dueling Double DQN (D3QN) [9] further refines these improvements, while Conservative Q-Learning (CQL) [10] promotes more conservative value estimation.

Policy-Based Methods optimize policies directly, making them effective in continuous action spaces but prone to high variance. Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [11] stabilizes learning through a clipped objective function, improving sample efficiency and robustness.

Actor-Critic Methods combine value- and policy-based approaches, where an actor selects actions and a critic evaluates them. Advantage Actor-Critic (A2C) [12] reduces variance, while its asynchronous variant (A3C) [12] accelerates learning. Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) [13] adapts DQN for continuous action spaces, with Twin Delayed Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (TD3) [14] improving stability by mitigating overestimation bias.

Planning Algorithms utilize environment models for decision-making rather than direct interaction. The Generalized Value Iteration Pruning (GIP) [15] algorithm makes value

iteration more tractable in partially observable environments, while PERSEUS [16], a randomized point-based method, scales efficiently to larger POMDPs.

B. Related studies

Several literature surveys have been performed in the past on topics related to RL and security testing. For instance, [17] presents a comprehensive literature review on the use of RL for intrusion detection, intrusion prevention, identity and access management and internet of things (IoT). The survey covers studies published between 2010 and 2021 in the Science Direct, ACM, IEEEExplore, and Springer databases. However, security testing is not directly considered. The study is similar to ours in the sense that it identifies a mapping of publications and topics without going into details.

A literature review of RL applications in cyber security covering penetration testing, intrusion detection and prevention of cyber security attacks is provided in [18]. The identified studies have been published between 2015 and 2021, and only marginally overlap our SMS. However, the protocol used for selecting the studies and the publication databases searched are not clearly defined.

A systematic review on the use of machine learning (ML) techniques for vulnerability detection using ML-based fuzzing has been presented in [19]. Fuzzing is one of the techniques employed for detecting vulnerabilities by providing unexpected and random data inputs to the SUT. The study uses the PRISMA framework (the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Meta-Analysis) [20]. The publications are collected from ScienceDirect, ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, SpringerLink, and Arxiv databases. Similarly to our study, an initial screening is made based on title and abstract. However, the keywords impose the presence of “fuzzing” in the search. In total 91 publications are reviewed, covering the years 2010-2024, resulting in a partial overlapping (9 publications) with our study, which can be seen as complementary and more comprehensive with respect to security testing.

II. STUDY DESIGN

The overarching research question that we would like to answer in this study is “*What is the current landscape of security testing techniques based on RL and what are the key trends and potential research directions?*”. More specifically, we are interested in exploring possible methods for designing and creating test cases to improve the validation and verification of different software systems and the tools, which allow testing using RL from the perspective of security. In conducting our study, we followed the protocol for performing systematic mapping studies (SMSs) outlined by Petersen et al. [4]. To initiate the protocol, we defined the following research questions:

- RQ1: What primary studies have been published and which are the most prominent publication venues for this topic?

- RQ2: Which security testing method is used for each study in conjunction with RL?
- RQ3: Which RL algorithms are used and for what purpose?
- RQ4: What is the available tool support developed by the studies?
- RQ5: Which application domains are targeted by the identified studies?
- RQ6: What techniques have been used for the evaluation of the approaches?

Search string. The following search terms were used to find the relevant literature are the following: (1) *security*, *securities*, (2) *testing*, *test*, *tests*, and (3) “*reinforcement learning*”. As one can notice, alternate spellings are considered in order to recognize as many correlated research studies to the topic as possible.

The search string is formed by connecting the search terms using the Boolean logical operators (e.g., *AND* and *OR*). The following search string was applied to the *title* and the *abstract* database fields to find the relevant research studies:

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(security OR securities) AND
(testing OR test OR tests) AND
"reinforcement learning"
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Research databases. The databases or the digital libraries where the search string was applied were the following: (1) ACM Digital Library, (2) IEEE Xplore, (3) ScienceDirect, (4) Scopus and (5) Web Of Science. These databases index most of the conferences, workshops, and journal publications related to the software engineering field [21].

Study selection criteria and procedures. The following inclusion criteria were applied for selecting primary studies:

- conference proceedings, early access articles, book chapters, and journal articles,
- studies written in English,
- studies published in the last 10 years (2014-2024)

We applied the following exclusion criteria to remove irrelevant studies:

- when similar studies on the same approach or tool were recognized within the same application domain, only the most recent one was retained,
- doctoral theses, reviews or books were not considered as primary studies,
- Secondary studies (e.g., literature reviews) were omitted,
- studies not subject to peer review such as white-papers, or studies published on public archives such as *arXiv*.

Study selection procedure. In the study selection procedure, we chose the relevant studies for review according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The selection procedure is divided into three phases:

- title and abstract level screening – In this phase, we read through the title and abstract parts of the studies in order to decide if the study is relevant to provide answers to the RQs;

- full-text level screening – The recognized studies above were analysed on the basis of full text. In this phase, the research studies were read, and inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied to them in order to choose the most relevant studies;
- snowballing [22] – the primary studies identified by the previous two phases were screened for the additional relevant literature. We performed this step in only one level of depth.

Study quality assessment checklist and procedure. In this part, the studies were assessed for their quality merit. The final selected studies were screened according to the following study quality assessment checklist [23]:

- 1) Are the goals in studies clearly defined?
- 2) Is the method or algorithm distinctly defined?
- 3) Are the assumptions or restrictions clear to a researcher?
- 4) Is the method subjected to validation in a case study or an experiment?
- 5) Is tool support discussed?
- 6) Is the case study pragmatic?
- 7) Are there multiple case studies used for validation?
- 8) Is there a qualitative comparison with different approaches?
- 9) Is there a quantitative comparison with different approaches?
- 10) Are the limitations or threats to validity clearly stated?

The answer to each question is ranked with a number of points: 2 - Fully answers the question, 1- partially answers the question, and 0 - it does not answer the question. We have ranked all primary studies based on the number of points obtained and selected the studies that scored at least 6 points.

III. RESULTS

After performing the initial search, 428 studies were identified from the selected publication databases as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
OVERVIEW OF DATABASES' SEARCH

Database:	Results:
IEEE	82
ScienceDirect	17
ACM DL	42
Scopus	196
Web Of Science	91
Total	428

After removing 216 duplicate studies and applying selection criteria, 151 publications were selected. Six more studies were removed after the title and abstract level screening and 9 studies after full-text reading, as shown in Figure 1. During reading the full text, we have also identified an additional 11 studies via snowballing. Lastly, after evaluating the quality of the studies, 47 primary studies were selected for further analysis.

Fig. 1. Number of identified primary studies at different levels of the protocol.

RQ1: identified primary studies and their publication venue

The distribution of these 47 publications per year is given in Fig. 2. As one can notice, the first relevant publication was identified in 2017, and the level of interest gradually increased towards 2024. We also point out that the search was completed in March 2024. 19 studies (40.4%) were published in proceedings of conferences and workshops, whereas 28 (59.6%) were published as journal articles.

Fig. 2. Number of studies per year.

RQ2: type of security testing method

The security testing methods used in conjunction with RL are shown in Table II. From the results, most of the studies (30) have targeted *penetration testing*. In this context, the focus is on automating the penetration testing process using RL algorithms to reduce human intervention and improve efficiency. For instance, studies [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], and [29] use RL models like DQN and hierarchical RL models to automatically find vulnerabilities in large networks. Additionally, [30] uses RL in the post-breach phase to evaluate system vulnerabilities after initial access.

A few studies employ hierarchical approaches, where action spaces are divided into smaller tasks to improve performance and tackle large, complex networks. For instance, [24], [31], [32] utilize hierarchical RL agents to break down complex PT tasks and efficiently find vulnerabilities in large networks, whereas [29] and [33] use multiple agents to parallelize the PT process, speeding up the identification of weak points in complex environments.

The work in study [34] uses capture-the-flag (CTF) challenges to simulate attack and defence scenarios, where RL agents attempt to "capture" vulnerabilities in an unknown network. [35] introduces social engineering elements into PT, simulating human-driven vulnerabilities as part of the automated test. Finally, several studies focus on improving the scalability and applicability of PT to various network sizes and configurations; study [36] utilizes generalized RL models that can be applied to different network topologies to test their vulnerabilities, while study [34] focuses on optimizing PT during the reconnaissance and exploitation phases.

Fuzz testing takes the second place with 7 studies with the primary goal to automate, optimize, and improve the effectiveness of security assessments through RL techniques. For instance, study [37] utilizes RL to optimize the mutation scheduling in the AFL fuzzing tool. This approach aims to improve the quality of mutation samples to generate better test cases, maximizing fuzzing coverage and finding new vulnerabilities. Study [38] introduces the DRLFCfuzzer tool to focus fuzzing on format-constrained input spaces. By modelling the fuzzing process as a MDP, this tool avoids generating invalid test cases, thereby improving efficiency. [39] uses RL to generate input sequences more effectively by learning which mutations are most likely to trigger security vulnerabilities. The RL agent continuously modifies input data based on rewards received from the fuzzing process, leading to better coverage. [40] employs RL to automate code mutation for fuzz testing in compilers. It generates multi-step mutations that increase the likelihood of discovering vulnerabilities such as memory leaks and crashes by prioritizing input sequences based on dynamic trace analysis.

Studies [41] and [42] focus on testing in specialized environments such as testing Android mobile devices in 4G/LTE networks and respectively in compilers, where RL is used to either adjust the mutation strategies or to mutate programs that trigger compiler errors. Studies [37] and [41] focus on increasing code coverage and identifying previously undiscovered vulnerabilities by intelligently selecting input sequences, either by finding new paths in the code that have not previously been covered or by generating weighted input sequences that prioritize inputs that increase code coverage.

Study [43] proposes a grey-box fuzzing method to optimize the detection of Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) vulnerabilities in Java web applications. This approach uses RL algorithms to optimize payload generation, increasing the efficiency of fuzz

testing for XSS by focusing on inputs that are more likely to bypass protection mechanisms. Finally, study [44] integrates RL with Z3 and SMT solvers for branch condition analysis, helping to improve the accuracy of input generation for fuzz testing. This hybrid approach allows the system to understand program logic more effectively, enabling better-targeted fuzz inputs.

Studies [45], [46], [47], [48], [49], [50], [51], and [52] focus on *vulnerability identification* by utilizing RL techniques to discover weaknesses in different systems, protocols, and hardware setups. [45] focuses on detecting XSS vulnerabilities in web applications. The RL algorithm generates and verifies attack vectors automatically, allowing it to bypass web application firewalls with increased efficiency. [46] and [51] apply RL to identify security weaknesses in cyber-physical systems (CPS) and smart grids. These studies use RL algorithms to pinpoint critical vulnerabilities and assess cascading failures that could result from simultaneous system element failures or cyberattacks. [47] identifies hardware trojans in integrated circuits using RL by exploring vast search spaces and generating malicious hardware designs that bypass existing detection techniques. [48] focuses on identifying vulnerabilities in SSL/TLS certificate verification by mutating certificates to find discrepancies in how they are processed. [49] and [50] target vulnerabilities in power systems, with [49] using RL to launch false data injection attacks and load-switching attacks. [50] models a multistage game between an attacker and a defender to find the weakest points in a smart grid system that could result in transmission line outages and blackouts. [52] focuses on testing and identifying vulnerabilities in anti-malware engines by mutating malware samples in order to explore weaknesses in malware detection tools.

Lastly, study [35] presents an adaptive stress-testing methodology called AST-SafeSec aimed at improving the safety and security analysis of cyber-physical systems. The primary objective of the AST-SafeSec methodology is to simultaneously analyse both the safety and security attributes of CPS. This approach helps to identify how random faults (e.g., sensor failures) and adversarial attacks could affect system performance and lead to dangerous outcomes.

TABLE II
LIST OF STUDIES BASED ON THE SOFTWARE TESTING TYPE

Testing Type	No.	Ref
Penetration testing	30	[24], [53], [35], [54], [25], [30], [26], [31], [55], [56], [57], [40], [58], [32], [59], [34], [60], [61], [62], [36], [63], [27], [28], [29], [64], [65], [66], [67], [33]
Fuzz testing	8	[37], [39], [38], [41], [40], [68], [43], [44], [42]
Vulnerability identification	6	[45], [46], [47], [48], [49], [50], [51], [52]
Stress testing	1	[69]

RQ3: which RL algorithms are used

Table III lists the RL algorithms identified in different studies. The DQN algorithm, and its variants like Dueling DQN, Double Deep Q-Learning, and Conservative Q-Learning, are widely employed in cybersecurity research. Studies like [24], [30], [26], [39], [46], and [55] use DQN to automate penetration testing, vulnerability assessment, and attack generation, particularly for smart grids and power systems. [48] explores DQN for automating certificate verification testing in SSL/TLS implementations. [57], with its DUSC-DQN algorithm, incorporates duelling network mechanisms and conservative Q-Learning to improve exploration and avoid overestimation in penetration testing path design. The INNES model (study [59]) uses DQN to improve the efficiency of data collection and model applicability for network security assessment. RIVER 2.0 (study [44]) leverages DQN for efficient fuzz testing, generating inputs for test cases and prioritizing them for better code coverage. The framework proposed in study [27] utilizes DQN to discover optimal attack paths based on network topology models. The NDSPI-DQN algorithm (study [28]) enhances exploration efficiency for penetration testing by incorporating noisy nets, Soft Q-learning, duelling architectures, prioritized experience replay, and intrinsic curiosity. Study [29] introduces a hierarchical multi-agent DRL architecture (HA-DRL) that leverages DQN for efficient penetration testing in complex networks. The double agent architecture (DAA) in study [33] utilizes DQN, DDQN, Dueling DQN, and D3QN in the exploiting phase to evaluate the highest reward gain during penetration testing. [70] leverages DDQN to generate payloads that bypass web application firewalls (WAFs) and uncover their vulnerabilities. Study [42] uses DQN for the automated generation of test suites for compiler fuzzing, learning to create valid programs and evaluating them based on feedback from execution traces. FuzzBoost, proposed in study [40], generates quality mutants for compiler fuzzing to reveal security vulnerabilities. DQN helps the model learn to create effective test inputs that can uncover compiler bugs. Study [67] identifies and remediates false data injection (FDI) attacks in DC micro-grids. The multi-agent approach allows for coordinated vulnerability assessment and defence strategies. In study [45], the authors develop an automated method for generating and verifying XSS attack vectors. D3QN with PER helps generate effective attack vectors faster and bypass Web Application Firewalls (WAFs).

Studies [35], [41], [60], [61], [63], and [51] use tabular Q-learning to generate attack sequences, train agents in network emulators, and identify optimal attack paths in smart grids. [60] particularly explores the trade-off between model-free learning and prior knowledge in a capture-the-flag scenario, demonstrating how tabular Q-learning can be combined with domain expertise for improved performance. [61] utilizes Q-learning in conjunction with a cyber threat knowledge graph to generate attacks and analyse vulnerabilities in an

TABLE III
LIST OF STUDIES BASED ON THE RL ALGORITHM USED

Category	Algorithm	Study ID	No
Value	DQN	[24], [35], [30], [26], [39], [46], [55], [48], [40], [43], [59], [44], [42], [27], [28], [29], [52], [67], [70]	19
	Q-Learning	[53], [35], [56], [41], [34], [60], [61], [62], [63], [64], [50], [51]	12
	DDQN	[43], [33], [70]	3
	Dueling DQN	[57], [33]	2
	Dueling DDQN	[45], [33]	2
	CQL	[57]	1
Policy	PPO	[25], [36], [40], [47], [54], [58]	6
	Policy Gradient	[43]	1
Actor-Critic	DDPG	[69], [38], [49], [67]	4
	A2C	[65], [66], [33]	3
	A3C	[34]	1
	TD3	[37]	1
Planning	GIP	[32]	1
	PERSEUS	[32]	1
	Random	[35]	1
	Not specified	[31]	1

air traffic management system. Study [63] utilizes tabular Q-learning within a capture-the-flag scenario, training agents to discover and exploit SQL injection vulnerabilities in web applications. Suggester, the intelligent agent in study [64], utilizes multi-objective reinforcement learning (MORL) to suggest effective attack strings for XSS vulnerability testing. Study [52] proposes the DQEAF framework to test anti-malware engines by generating malware samples that can evade detection. In their multistage game model for smart grid security analysis study [50] the authors employ the Q-learning algorithm to find attack sequences that cause damage to the system. This game involves an active attacker and a passive defender, providing insights into potential vulnerabilities. In [53], a repeated game is formulated to mimic the real-life interactions between the adversaries of the modern electric power system. The solution of the game is based on the Q-learning algorithm. The learned attacker's and defender's optimal strategies give significant information (such as vulnerable elements) about a cyber-physical power system. A framework based on an improved Q-Learning algorithm for automated distributed web hacking is introduced in study [56], with interconnected agents facilitating information exchange and improving convergence speed. The work in study [62] utilizes the nearest sequence memory (NSM) Q-learning algorithm for false data injection (FDI) attacks on power systems, discovering vulnerable spots for injection.

Study [54] leverages PPO to generate hardware trojans that can evade known detection techniques. Study [25], in its RL automated penetration testing (RLAPT) method, uses PPO to train an attacker agent with diverse attack results. Study [40] adopts PPO in the EPPTA framework for agent training due to its adaptability to environmental changes and stability. Study [58] combines the Generative Pre-trained Transformer language model with PPO for black box testing of web application firewalls. The SetTron policy

architecture (study [36]) for zero-shot generalization in penetration testing can be solved with PPO. Study [47] proposes an automated framework for generating hardware trojans that evade detection techniques. PPO helps the model learn to insert trojans strategically to remain undetected by common methods.

The DDPG algorithm is utilized in studies [69], [38], and [49]. For instance, study [69] incorporates a DDPG RL agent's policy for adaptive stress-testing in a cyber-physical systems (CPS) security analysis framework. Study [38] uses DDPG to address the multi-dimensional state and action space problem in fuzz testing. Study [49] employs DDPG with limited prior knowledge in an LSTM-based model to simulate false data injection and load-switching attacks on load frequency control systems. The Link tool, presented in study [65], utilizes A2C to automatically generate payloads for detecting reflected XSS vulnerabilities in web applications. The double agent architecture (DAA) in study [33] employs A2C in the structuring phase to gather information about the network and its elements. Study [37] leverages the TD3 algorithm for efficient fuzz testing, solving state and action space problems. Study [43] uses DQN, DDQN, and Policy Gradient for XSS vulnerability detection, optimizing payload generation. Study [34] uses the A3C algorithm to automate the investigation and exploitation phases of penetration testing. Study [66] uses the A2C RL algorithm for website hacking as a capture-the-flag scenario for penetration testers.

The Intelligent Automated Penetration Testing Framework (IAPTF) in study [32] leverages the GIP algorithm, alongside the Randomized point-based value iteration algorithm (PERSEUS), to automate sequential decision-making in penetration testing. This framework divides network complexity into smaller clusters, enabling agents to efficiently perform penetration testing in large-scale scenarios.

A. RQ4: available tool-support for performing security testing

We have only found 4 studies with tool support explicitly provided as shown in Table IV. The link to the page of the tool is provided as a footnote.

TABLE IV
TOOLS USED FOR SECURITY TESTING

Name of the tool	Study ID
GPTFuzzer ¹	[58]
INNEN ²	[59]
RIVER 2.0 ³	[44]
AgentWebModel developed in OpenAIGym ⁴	[66]

¹<https://github.com/hongliangliang/gptfuzzer>

²<https://github.com/liqianyu513/INNEN-model>

³<https://unibuc-cs.github.io/river>

⁴<https://github.com/FMZennaro/gym-agentwebmodel>

RQ5: application domains targeted

Table V lists the application domains where the approaches were applied. This can help researchers to find all relevant studies in the domain of interest. Most approaches in the studies are used to perform testing and assess the vulnerabilities in the network security domain. However, the studies can be further grouped based on their scalability on different sizes of networks. For instance, the work presented in [24], [25], [26] can be used to perform penetration testing on large networks, while studies [35], [40], [65] propose methods to assess small to medium size networks with poor scalability on networks with a higher number of elements. Several studies ([49], [55], [61], [62], [69]) can be also applied in the CPS domain, although they achieve the best results when applied in the electric smart grid systems. Studies [53], [46], [50], [51], [67] are used mainly within the electric power grid scenarios. Study [24] assesses the security of a network providing remote and local vulnerability exploitation. Study [37] is used for testing metaverse software by enhancing the test case generation loop in AFL tools. Study [45] is used in the web application domain to test mainly XSS web attack type. Study [69] tackles the problem of abnormal behaviours that affects CPS performance due to possible sensor faults and attacks. Study [54] proposes a technique and an automated framework for HT generation that can bypass HT detection techniques. The approach in [46] assesses the cyber-physical electrical power systems (EPS) in wind integrated power systems.

TABLE V
LIST OF STUDIES BASED ON THE DOMAINS IN WHICH THEY ARE USED

Domain name	No.	Study reference
Network security	20	[24], [35], [25], [30], [26], [31], [57], [40], [32], [59], [34], [60], [36], [27], [28], [29], [64], [65], [66], [33]
Power systems	5	[53], [46], [50], [51], [67]
Cyber-physical systems (CPS)	5	[69], [55], [49], [61], [62]
Web Application Firewalls	3	[45], [58], [70]
Web applications	2	[56], [43]
Compiler validation	2	[40], [42]
Hardware Trojans detection	2	[54], [47]
Metaverse	1	[37]
PDF processing programs	1	[39]
Software programs	1	[38]
Certificate verification in SSL/TLS implementations	1	[48]
Mobile device LTE network traffic	1	[41]
x86 programs	1	[44]
SQL injection	1	[63]
Anti-malware engines	1	[52]

RQ6: evaluation method of the proposed approach

The evaluation of the methods and tools developed in the proposed approaches can be largely distributed in several categories as shown in Table VI. Simulation-based evaluation leverages controlled environments where RL and other techniques can be safely tested at scale, focusing on

performance and robustness in a risk-free setting. Experiment-based evaluation focuses on testing methods in live, real-world environments, providing high practical relevance, but with potential risks and complexity. Case study-based evaluation analyses the application of methods in specific real-world scenarios, providing detailed insights into the practical benefits and challenges of the methods, though without direct experimentation. Our results show that 11 studies performed simulation-based evaluation, 30 studies performed experiment-based evaluation, 4 performed case study-based evaluation, while 3 studies do not mention any method.

TABLE VI
TYPE OF EVALUATION

Evaluation method	No.	Study ID
Simulation	11	[69], [46], [56], [58], [32], [34], [60], [62], [63], [29], [50], [51]
Experiment	30	[24], [37], [45], [35], [25], [31], [39], [55], [47], [38], [48], [57], [41], [40], [40], [43], [32], [59], [49], [61], [36], [63], [42], [27], [28], [29], [64], [52], [67], [33], [70]
Case study	4	[53], [54], [26], [65]
N/A	3	[30], [44], [66]

IV. DISCUSSION

This SMS provides a comprehensive analysis of RL applications in security testing, identifying key trends, gaps, and future research directions based on 47 primary studies. **Key Trends and Gaps** Penetration testing emerges as the primary focus (30 studies), predominantly using Q-learning-based algorithms like DQN, highlighting RL’s role in automating complex attack paths. Fuzzing, though explored (8 studies), remains less prevalent. A significant gap exists in applying RL to diverse domains and environments, particularly for security regression testing, where ensuring system integrity amid evolving software is crucial. The generalization of RL-based algorithms is also a challenge, as most studies focus on specific use cases without evaluating broader applicability, particularly in dynamic network environments. The prevalence of DQN (19 studies) and tabular Q-learning (12 studies) underscores a reliance on foundational approaches, suggesting opportunities to explore advanced methods like policy gradient and actor-critic algorithms. Evaluation methodologies primarily involve simulations (11 studies) and experimental setups (30 studies), with limited real-world case studies, indicating a need for standardized benchmarks and shared testing environments. Notably, no studies address DevOps or DevSecOps, despite their critical role in integrating security testing across the SDLC.

Research Directions Future studies should:

- Develop advanced RL algorithms, such as policy-based and actor-critic methods, to enhance generalization and adapt to real-world applications, including multi-agent RL for adversarial simulations.

- Establish standardized testing environments, benchmark datasets, and evaluation metrics to improve comparability and reproducibility.
- Investigate RL for security regression testing to ensure evolving systems maintain robust security over time.
- Expand RL-driven penetration testing to improve adaptability to unknown networks and reduce false positives.
- Enhance tool support for industry adoption.

Overall, RL-based security testing presents significant potential, but addressing these gaps is essential for broader applicability and real-world impact.

V. THREATS TO VALIDITY

This section outlines potential threats to the validity of this SMS.

Internal validity: Selection bias may have occurred due to predefined inclusion criteria and search terms, potentially overlooking relevant studies. To mitigate this, backward snowballing was applied, and all publications were reviewed by multiple researchers with disagreements resolved collaboratively.

External validity: Excluding grey literature and limiting the study to the past 10 years may affect generalizability. Future research could expand the scope to include older and unpublished studies.

Construct validity: Reliance on specific search terms and databases may have excluded studies using different terminology or less prominent venues. However, the search strategy was designed to align with the research focus, using well-established databases in software engineering.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This SMS aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of security testing using RL algorithms by analyzing 47 relevant studies. Our findings highlight a growing trend toward the use of RL, particularly in automating penetration testing, with DQN and its variants being the most frequently employed algorithms.

However, several research gaps persist. There is a notable lack of studies on RL for security regression testing, as well as the absence of standardized benchmarks, datasets, and evaluation metrics. Additionally, the surveyed literature does not adequately consider DevOps and DevSecOps methodologies, despite their importance in modern software development. Challenges related to generalization, robustness, and interpretability also limit the practical applicability of RL-based approaches in security testing.

Overall, RL-driven security testing is an emerging field with significant potential. This study contributes by mapping the current research landscape and outlining key directions to address existing challenges, supporting future advancements in both academic and practical domains.

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